

ASSESSMENT OF MORTALITY, MORBIDITY AND CLINICAL OUTCOMES IN PATIENT'S SUFFERING WITH WORLD PANDEMIC DISEASE-SARS COVID-19

Dr. B. Chandrika^{1*}, D. Veera Prasad², G. Vaishnavi³, A. Gouri Supriya⁴, B. Sandhya Rani⁵, D. Manindra⁶, D. Yashwitha⁷, G. Shashi Kiran⁸, S. D. Nayeem⁹, M. Vinod Kumar¹⁰

¹Pharm D, Assistant Professor of Dhanvanthari Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Sujatha Nagar, Kothagudem.

^{2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10}B. Pharm [IV Year students] of Dhanvanthari Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Sujatha Nagar, Kothagudem.

Article Received on 05 June 2026,
Article Revised on 25 June 2026,
Article Published on 01 July 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21151933>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. B. Chandrika

Pharm D, Assistant Professor of
Dhanvanthari Institute of
Pharmaceutical Sciences, Sujatha
Nagar, Kothagudem.

How To Cite This Article: Dr. B. Chandrika^{1*}, D. Veera Prasad², G. Vaishnavi³, A. Gouri Supriya⁴, B. Sandhya Rani⁵, D. Manindra⁶, D. Yashwitha⁷, G. Shashi Kiran⁸, S. D. Nayeem⁹, M. Vinod Kumar¹⁰ (2026). Assessment of Mortality, Morbidity and Clinical Outcomes in Patient's Suffering with World Pandemic Disease-Sars Covid-19. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(7), 1440–1454.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Background: Novel coronavirus is a world pandemic disease which cause 3.7 million deaths around the world. This novel coronavirus is also called as severe acute respiratory syndrome -corona virus 2 and covid -19 which is highly contagious and cause common symptoms like cold, cough to life threatening complications like septic shock and multiorgan failure.^[1] **AIM:** The objective of this study is to analyze death rate and recovery rate in covid-19 patients by using statistical analysis method that is spearman's correlation. **Materials And Methods:** Death rate and recovery rate was assessed with the statistical method-spearman's correlation. This spearman's correlation is a non-test which is used to for measuring the degree of association between the two variables that is association of average CT score with death rate, association of average saturation levels with death rate and association of average days of hospitalization with death rate. **Results:** In our study it was found that high CT severity and low saturation

level are the major cause of mortality in covid- 19 patients.

Conclusion: Our study which aim's in assessing the mortality and morbidity in people who tested positive for covid-19 demonstrates that death rate is significantly increase with low saturation and high CT severity.

KEYWORDS: Covid-19, SARS-CoV-2, Mortality Rate, Recovery Rate, CT Severity Score, Oxygen Saturation, Spearman's Correlation, Clinical Outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

SARS COV-2 is a Beta coronavirus causing the current covid-19 out break, and is seventh coronavirus that is known to infect humans.^[2] This coronavirus belonging to the family coronaviridae mostly affecting human beings through zoonotic transmission.^[3] The structure of the corona virus is special or pleomorphic enveloped particles containing single standard [positive sense RNA. The human incubation period was up to 14 days mean and median incubation period was 8 and 12.^[4] Clinical manifestations may vary and include as symptomatic carrier status. IT is same both in symptomatic and as symptomatic patients. Coronavirus classified on the basis of the crown or halo-like appearance of the envelope glycoproteins and on characteristic features of chemistry and replication. Coronavirus resemble each other in morphology and chemical structure.^[5] Symptoms of covid -19 include sore throat, fever, rhinitis, headache gastrointestinal symptoms, loss of smell and taste. No. of people remains as symptomatic can be able to transmit the virus. Till June 8th 2021 total corona cases in india 28,996,949 and overall death rate is 351,344 and recovery rate is 27,341,462.^[6] Till June 7, 2021 covid 19 deaths around the world 3.7 million people.^[7] Pathological mechanism Of sars cov 2 -sars cov 2 shares genetic sequence to sars cov 80% similarity and to MERS cov with 50% similarity. This novel coronavirus made of spike [S], membrane [m], nucleocapsid [n], envelope [e] proteins.^[8] S protein helps in binding to the in s₁ domain and s₂ subunit helps in membrane fusion. ACE-2 is the cellular receptor for sarscov and sars cov2. This ACE 2 receptors is present in the upper respiratory system. In the 2 types of alveolar epithelial cells in the lungs, heart, pancreas, endothelial cells, enterocytes, tubular epithelium in kidneys. When the virus binds to ACE receptor, TMPRSS2 a serine protease involves in s protein priming and cleavage of the spike. Virus enters by endosomal pathway.^[9] Low P^H and cathepsin -L protease provide favorable endosomal micro environment for the delivery of sars cov-2 genome in to the cytosol where further replication occurs and spread to other body parts. Apoptosis and necrosis occur in infected cells and that triggers the inflammatory response cause recruitment of inflammatory cells. SARS cov 2

increase the lymphocytopenia and cause high secretions of cytokine cells cause cytokine storm. This elevated cytokine levels, TNF alpha, chemokines may cause hyper inflammation and this may lead to multiorgan failure.^[10] ACE 2 receptors expressed in epithelial cells in lungs, colon, small intestine, tubular cells of the kidney, neuronal and glial cells in the brain, enterocytes, vascular endothelial cells, cardiomyocytes and smooth muscle cells.^[11]

PERCENTAGE OF PEOPLE AFFECTED WITH DIFFERENT SYMPTOMS

According to a study fatigue [19%], cough[85%], headache [78%] where the most common symptoms. General symptoms – myalgia [73.2%], rhinitis [70%], sore throat[65%], fever[65%], dyspnea [51.1], GI symptoms [42%].^[12]

NEUROLOGICAL SYMPTOMS

-Loss of smell

-Coronavirus affects smell sensation by affecting the function of supporting cells but not by directly affecting neurons.

This is because olfactory sensory neurons do not express the gene which encodes ACE2 receptor proteins, but expressed in structural and metabolic cells which support olfactory sensory neurons.^[13]

Loss of taste- limited data available on mechanisms involved in the pathogenesis of taste disorders in covid-19. But some RNA- sequencing studies say that the epithelial cells present on the tongue express ACE2 receptor.^[14] So, it was one of the hypotheses saying indirect damage of taste receptors by infecting epithelial cells may cause taste disturbance.

➤ **Headache**

Corona virus -2 binds to ACE 2 receptors on endings of trigeminal nerves within in the nasal cavity and cause trigemino vascular activation, along with systemic inflammation.^[15] Viral load present in nasal cavity and active infection at close to cranial nerves and differential immune response is the primary trigger for headache in covid 19 patients.

➤ **Gastrointestinal symptoms [Nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal pain]**

SARS covid-2 cause ACE 2 modifications in the gut that increases the susceptibility to intestinal inflammation and diarrhea.^[16]

➤ **Respiratory symptoms**

When lungs infected with covid -19 the affected area swells and changes occur in the surface properties of pulmonary capillaries. So, resistance to the flow increased. Due to this vascular resistance WBC stays in the same position for longer time in affected capillaries and nearby capillaries, when the pulmonary pressure is high wbc's are squeezed into interstitial space to change from negative to positive value. This positive pressure causes the fluid to leak to alveolar space and thus degrades the lung function.^[17]

STAGES OF SYMPTOMS

➤ **ASYMPTOMATIC OR PRESYMPTOMATIC INFECTION**

Individuals who test positive for SARS- covid-19 but no symptoms.

➤ **MILD ILLNESS**

Individuals who are having any of the symptoms of sars covid -19 [e.g., headache, muscle pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, fever, cough, sore throat, malaise, loss of taste and smell] but do not have SOB, dyspnea, or abnormal chest imaging.

➤ **MODERATE ILLNESS**

Individuals having oxygen saturation [SpO₂] > 94% on room air.

➤ **SEVERE ILLNESS**

Individuals who are having spO₂ <94% on room air a ratio of arterial partial pressure of oxygen to fraction of inspired oxygen [PaO₂/ FiO₂] <300mm Hg, respiratory frequency >30 breaths /min, or lung infiltrates >50%.

➤ **CRITICAL ILLNESS**

Individuals who have respiratory failure, septic shock, and/or multiple organ failure.^{[18][19]}

➤ **DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA TO DETECT COVID - 19 INFECTION**

There are no specific clinical features that can distinguish covid-19 from other viral respiratory infection. But some of the studies suggesting that loss of smell and taste are the symptoms that are most strongly associated with a positive sarscov -2 test.^[20] -development of dyspnea – after several days of infection is also suggested covid-19.

Nucleic acid amplification testing [NAAT] with reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction [rt PCR] assay to detect sarscov – 2 RNA from the upper respiratory tract is the diagnostic test for covid-19. Rapid isothermal test may be less sensitive.

Negative NAAT results – if false negative results occur repeat test must be done to confirm the diagnosis. Other diagnostic markers crp,ldh,ferritin,d,dimers,il6 are used by to detect the severity of the disease.^[21]

THERAPEUTIC MANAGEMENT

According to a panel recommendation.^{[22] [23]}

MILD TO MODERATE, NOT HOSPITALIZED	NO RISK FOR PROGRESSION OF THE DISEASE- supportive treatment RISK FOR DISEASE PROGRESSION- any of following combination Bamlanivimab plus etesevimab Casirivimab plus imedivimab
HOSPITALIZED BUT NO NEED	Use of remdesivir may recommended
HOSPITALIZED AND REQUIRE OXYGEN	Remdesivir plus dexamethasone
NEED OF HIGH FLOW/NIV	Dexamethasone dexona plus remedesivir add tocilizumab to above any of combination
SEVERE ILLNESS	Dexamethasone plus tocilizumab

COMORDIDITIES

➤ Hypertension

A condition in which the force of the blood against the artery wall is too high. Usually, hypertension is defined as blood pressure above 140/190 and considered as severe if the pressure is above 180/120. Experimental studies suggesting that activation of RAS may play role in covid 19.

ACE-2 is the pivotal receptor for sarscov – 2 to enter host cells and provides thus a link between covid 19 and RAAS. It was anticipated that drugs modulating the RAAS including and up regulation of ACE 2 may increases the risk for infection with SAR cov 2.^[24] Sars imbalance may cause serious organ injury.^[25]

DIABETES MELLITUS

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disease characterized by elevated levels of blood glucose. Most common is type 2 diabetes it occurs when the body becomes resistant to insulin. In type 1 diabetes insulin dependent diabetes pancreas produce little or no insulin.

➤ ASSOCIATION OF COVID 19 WITH DIABETES MELLITUS

These are the following potential mechanisms that may increase the susceptibility for covid 19 in patients having DM.

- 1 – Having higher affinity for cellular binding and efficient virus entry
- 2 – Decreases in viral clearance
- 3 – Reduced T cell function
- 4 – Increased susceptibility to hyperinflammation and cytokine storm syndrome
- 5 – Presence of cardiovascular disease. Hyperglycemia may persist for 3 years recovery from Covid 19.^[26]

➤ AGE ASSOCIATION WITH COVID 19

Very elderly patients have high mortality rate because of recurrence of comorbidities and less immunity, so viral alert signals are much slower.^[27]

➤ OBESITY ASSOCIATION WITH COVID 19

People with over weight (BMI>40) also at increased risk. Obesity may impair the immune function and decrease the lung capacity and make ventilation more difficult. Amount of fat deposited in our body parts that decreases the adiponectin which directly protects the lungs.^[28] Adipose tissue also helpful for inducing low grade inflammation. The constant low-grade inflammation induced by obesity results in diminished T cells activity.^[29] Obesity cause decreased viral clearance and cause increase in viral load.^{[30] [31]} CVA ASSOCIATION WITH COVID-19-S protein and ACE 2 receptor expression on cardiac muscle cells may play role in pathogenesis in covid 19 induced cardiovascular disease.^[32]

➤ RESPIRATORY DISEASES ASSOCIATION WITH COVID 19

Due to their poor underlying lung reserve and increased expression of angiotensin-converting enzyme 2 (ACE-2) receptor in the small air ways cause lung damage.^[33]

➤ GENDER ASSOCIATION WITH COVID 19

Being a male is also a risk factor for getting covid 19 infection. This is because using a single-cell RNA-sequencing analysis it was detected that ACE 2 expression is more in males than females. Blocking estrogen receptors increased the mortality in female mice due to SARS-COV infection suggesting that estrogen receptors may have role in blocking some viral infection.^[34]

NEED FOR THE WORK

- 1 – To assess the type of symptoms in covid positive patients
- 2 – To assess the severity of lung damage in the patients who test positive for covid 19
- 3 – To assess the recovery rate in patients
- 4 – To assess the comorbid conditions
- 5 – To assess no.of days patients get hospitalized
- 6 – To assess the requirement of ventilation and oxygen supply to patients
- 7 – To assess death rate in covid positive patients.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To provide both pharmacological and nonpharmacological treatments.
2. To provide effective treatment and ventilation support based on patient response.
3. To provide the combinational treatment and other drugs in the early stage of disease to attain the best therapeutic response.
4. To monitor the over dosage of drugs which cause life threatening complications.
5. To counsel the patient regarding self – care about medication adherence about the diet and about sleeping positions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. STUDY SITE : GOVERNMENT GENERAL HOSPITALS, KOTHAGUDEM.

2. STUDY TYPE : PROSPECTIVE OBSERVATIONAL STUDY

3. STUDY PERIOD : 3 MONTHS

3. 4-STUDY CRITERIA

3.4.1- INCLUSION CRITERIA

- i. Covid positive patients.
- ii. Age : 10-110 years

3.4.2. EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- i. pregnancy and lactating women
- ii. women who are planning to conceive
- iii. Severe kidney failure, liver failure.

3.5. SOURCE OF DATA

- i. Patient data records

- ii. Patient demographic details
- iii. About comorbid conditions
- iv. No. of days on treatment
- v. Severity of disease
- vi. Low oxygen levels.

3.6 – FORMS INCLUDED IN THE STUDY.

- i. Data collection from including patient
- ii. Demographic details, type of symptoms, comorbid conditions, diagnosis, no. of days hospitalized, oxygen requirement.

3.7 STUDY PROCEDURE

- i. Subjects tested positive for covid-19 based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- ii. Demographic data collected from patient records.
- iii. Patients were analyzed for comorbid condition.
- iv. Severity categorized based on HRCT report and symptoms and saturation levels, no. of Days patient hospitalized.
- v. Data collected through out 3 months from 203 patients was analyzed.
- vi. Statistical Analysis: Spearsman's Correlation.

RESULTS

GENDER	TOTAL NO. OF PATIENTS
MALE	162
FEMALE	41

AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION

AGE	10-30	30-60	60-90	90-110
MALE	10	112	39	1
FEMALE	1	27	13	0
TOTAL	11	139	52	1

AVERAGEAGEOFFEMALES = 51.79798 + 13.27219

AGEOFFMALES = 51.65517 + 13.41859

DISEASE OUTCOME

DEATH RATIO	RECOVERY RATIO
17%	83%

COMORBIDITIES

COMORBIDITY	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
HTN	55	13	68
DM	57	10	67
CVA	09	02	11
ASTHAMA	07	00	07
COPD	08	00	08

SYMPTOMS.

SYMPTOMS	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
SOB	90	1	91
HEADACHE	12	06	18
FEVER	146	35	181
COUGH	129	30	159
COLD	20	06	26
GENERAL WEAKNESSWITH BODY PAINS	46	14	60
THROAT ACHE	09	0	09

AGEUSIA	03	03	06
ANOSMIA	04	01	05
BURNING MICTURATION	0	09	09
LOOSE STOOLS	10	01	11

CT SCORE FOR 25

CT-SCORE	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
0-5	19	06	25
5-10	65	12	77
10-15	56	19	75
15-20	19	04	23
20-25	03	0	03

S.No	Clinical Parameters	Recovered	Death	R value
1	Average CT score	10.645+4.24755	16.668+5.280	0.7
2	Average Oxygen Saturation	91.408+6.895	86.647+939	1
3	Average Days Of Hospitalization	5.344+5.858	6.403+121	-0.4

R Value significant if positive

Statistical methods

Spearman,s correlation was done for average CT score and the values were found to be $10.645+4.24755$ for death rate, $16.668+5.280$ to for recovery rate and the R value was found to be 0.7. For average oxygen saturation spearman,s correlation was done and the values were $91.408+6.895$ for death rate, $86.647+939$ and the R value is 1. Spearman,s correlation was also done for average days of hospitalization and values were $5.344+5.858$ for death rate, $6.403+121$ for recovery rate and R value is -0.4 .

DISCUSSION

Covid -19 pneumonia – world pandemic causing mild symptoms like cold, cough, to life threatening complications like pneumonia, multi organ failure. This study provides death rate and recovery rate in patients who tested positive SARS cov – 2 by considering average saturation levels, average days of hospitalization and average CT severity.

➤ CLINICAL OUTCOME IN ASSOCIATION WITH GENDER

Of the total study population male ratio is 80% is high when compared with female ratio 20% so, males have bad prognosis when compared with females. This was due to ACE 2 expression is higher in males then females. Our results are similar to the study conducted by George M.B wire in which males are more to covid-19 infection then females.

➤ CLINICAL OUTCOME IN ASSOCIATION WITH AGE

In our study average age of males is $51.65517+13.41859$ and females is $51.79798+13.27219$. This was due to many comorbid conditions, and decreased immunity. So old age people have high risk of death rate. Our results are similar to the study conducted by center for disease control and prevention.

DISEASE OUTCOME

Of the total study population 17% were died and 83% were recovered.

COMORBIDITIES

➤ **HYPERTENSION:** In our study hypertension (34%) is leading comorbidity that causes bad prognosis in people suffering with hypertension. This was due to up regulation of the ACE 2 receptors. Our results are similar to the study conducted by M Salazar.

➤ **DIABETES MELLITUS:** In our study (32%) of the people suffering with diabetes are at increased risk for covid 19 infection. Our results are similar to the study conducted by Soo

Lim et al. This may be due to increased expression of ACE 2 in lungs of patients with diabetes, diminished T cells activation, decreased viral clearance may cause bad prognosis.

➤ **CARDIOVASCULAR DISORDERS:** In our study 2% of people have bad prognosis if they had previous history of cardiovascular disorders. Our results are similar to the study conducted by Manish Bansal et al. This may be due to damage of myocardial tissue.

➤ **COPD AND ASTHMA:** In our study population 5% and 4% of people had bad prognosis due to COPD and ASTHMA respectively. This may be due to decreased lung reserve capacity due to high expression of ACE 2 in airways.

CLINICAL OUTCOME IN ASSOCIATION WITH SYMPTOMS

In our study population fever, cough and SOB have higher incidence in patients tested positive for COVID-19. So, patients with high fever, severe cough and shortness of breath may have bad prognosis.

CLINICAL OUTCOME IN ASSOCIATION WITH AVERAGE CT SCORE

In our study death rate and recovery rate by taking Spearman's correlation in people having average CT severity score is 10.645 ± 4.24755 and 16.668 ± 5.280 respectively and the R value is 0.7. Patients having high CT score may have high risk of death rate.

CLINICAL OUTCOME IN ASSOCIATION WITH AVERAGE OXYGEN SATURATION

In our study by taking Spearman's correlation recovery rate in association with average oxygen saturation is 91.408 ± 6.895 and death rate is 86.647 ± 939 and the R value was found to be 1. Patients with low saturation levels may have high risk of death rate.

CLINICAL OUTCOME IN ASSOCIATION WITH AVERAGE DAYS OF HOSPITALISATION

Death rate and recovery rate in our study by taking Spearman's correlation is 5.344 ± 5.858 and 6.403 ± 121 respectively. So, the R is -0.4. So, it was found that average days of hospitalization have no role in predicting death rate.

CONCLUSION

By conducting survey on SARS-COVID-19 we concluded that the vaccination is pivotal in eradicating the pandemic. Also we came to know the severity of the disease and its symptoms.

We came to know the importance of isolation of patients and importance of eradicating its spread.

REFERENCES

1. The COVID-19 epidemic; Thirumalaisamy P Velavan, Christian G Meyer; Tropical medicine & international health, 2020; 25(3): 278.
2. Transmission of SARS COV 2; implications for infection prevention precautions; WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION.
3. Determine the most common clinical symptoms in COVID-19 patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis; J. Prev. Med. Hyg., 2020 Sep; 61(3).
4. The incubation period during the pandemic of COVID-19: a systematic review and meta analysis; Wafa Dhouib, Jihen Maatoug et al; volume 10, Article number: 101[2021]
5. Considerations for diagnostics covid-19 tests : Olivier Vandenberg, Delphine Martiny, Zisis Kozlakidi review 19: 171-183 Darius N.K. Quansah.
6. Nature Reviews Microbiology volume 19, pages 171–183 (2021) Johnel fle in June7; 2021).
7. Corona viruses medical microbiology; 4th edition. Galveston (TX); University of Texas Medical Branch at Galveston; 1996. chapter 60.
8. COVID-19: Current understanding of its pathophysiology, Clinical presentation and treatment; volume 97; issue 1147.
9. Pathogenesis of COVID-19 from a cell biology perspective; Robert J., Mason. Effect of covid 19 on the Organs; Uday Jain; August 3; 2020.
10. Symptom Diary–Based Analysis of Disease Course among Patients with Mild Coronavirus Disease, Germany, 2020; Volume 27, Number 5—May 2021.
11. How COVID-19 Causes Loss of Smell Olfactory support cells, not neurons, are vulnerable to novel coronavirus infection; By KEVIN JIANG July 24, 2020 Research.
12. Volume 748, 23 March 2021, 135694 Smell and taste disorder rsin COVID-19: From pathogenesis to clinical features and outcomes.
13. Gonzalez – Martinezetal, 2020 Headache during SARS – COV -2 infection as an early symptoms associated with a more being course of disease: a case – control study. Eur. J. Neurol., 10. 1111/ ene. 14718.
14. Coronaetal, 2020. Headache: A striking prodromal and persistent symptom, predictive of COVID-19 Clinical evolution. Cephalalgia.
15. Gastrointestinal symptoms associated with COVID-19: impact on the gut microbiome;

- Sonia Villapol. *Transl. Res.*, 2020 Dec.
16. Lung Damage Mechanisms For COVID-19 and Other Lung Infections, and Driving Force in Leukocyte Recruitment and Migration Jianqing Wu et al.
 17. Tostmann A, Bradley J, Bousema T, et al. Strong associations and moderate predictive value of early symptoms for SARS-CoV-2 test positivity among healthcare workers, the Netherlands, March 2020. *Euro Surveill* 2020; 25.
 18. Symptom Diary-Based Analysis of Disease Course among patients with mild coronavirus disease, Germany, 2020; volume 27, 5-May 2021.
 19. Increased levels of ferritin on admission predicts intensive care unit mortality in patients with COVID-19; Volume 156, Issue 7, 9 April 2021.
 20. Laboratory diagnosis of coronavirus disease-2019; Chenxi Li et al; volume 510, November 2020, Pages 35-46.
 21. IDSA Guideline on the Treatment and Management of Patients with COVID- 19; Published by IDSA on 4/11/2020. Last updated, 6/3/2021.
 22. COVID-19 Treatment guidelines. NIH [NATIONAL INSTITUTES OF HEALTH]
 23. Hypertension, a Moving Target in COVID-19, Current Views and Perspective; Carmine Savoia, Massimo V, Reinhold Kreutz; 2021; 128: 1062–1079.
 24. COVID-19 patients with hypertension are at potential risk of worsened organ injury, Fei Xia et al; Published: 12 February 2021.
 25. COVID-19 and diabetes mellitus: from pathophysiology to clinical management, Soo Lim, Michael; *Nature Reviews Endocrinology* volume 17, pages 11–30 (2021) Cite this article.
 26. Covid-19: Why are age and obesity risk factors for serious disease? 16 May 2021, 100311.
 27. Ouchi N, Parker JL, Lugus JJ, Walsh K. Adipokines in inflammation and metabolic disease. *Nat Rev Immunol.* 2011; 11(2): 85–97.
 28. Ouchi N, Parker JL, et al Adipokines in inflammation and metabolic disease. *Nat. Rev. Immunol.*, 2011; 11(2): 85–97.
 29. Mescher MF, Agarwal P, Casey KA, Gerner M, Hammerbeck CD, et al. Signal required for programming effector and memory development by CD8+ T cells. *Immunol. Rev.*, 2006; 211: 81–92.
 30. COVID-19 and cardiovascular disease. From basic mechanisms to clinical perspectives; Masataka Nishiga, Dao Wen Wang; *Nature reviews cardiology* volume 17, page 543-558.
 31. Impact of COPD on COVID-19 prognosis; A national wide population-based study in

South Korea; Sang Chul Lee, Scientific reports volume 11, Article number: 3735 [2021].

32. Why men are more vulner able to covid-19 than women; George M. B wire; 2020 May 28.